

Controlling Public Programs and Investment

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Historically, there has been no concern for evaluating public programs in general and social programs in particular. For years, the production of technical knowledge in the pursuit of improving public sector management standards has always been much more focused on program design processes than on those related to its implementation and evaluation.

There is, however, evidence that this historical disinterest is rapidly diminishing. The crisis and the interruption of a long cycle of economic growth deepened the social inequalities present in the country's reality.

In turn, the structural reforms undertaken in the 2000s - trade opening and integration, state reform, privatization, among others - further widened these asymmetries as they increased unemployment, made the remaining jobs precarious and, consequently, reduced employment real wages. The unfavourable economic situation has caused an increase in demand for social actions and services, especially those of a compensatory nature.

From 1987 to the present, more than two hundred privatization operations have been carried out, resulting in a global cash flow of billions of Euro, considering millions for capital increases of the privatized companies themselves. Privatization operations despite this diversity, the sector where privatization has assumed particular importance, both due to the volume of operations and the structural changes that stimulated it, was the financial sector.

The privatizations of so-called utilities, requiring structural reforms, namely in terms of sectorized regulation and the restructuring and financial balance of business units, have been delayed to the detriment of the financial sector and some good quality or small industrial companies. In reality, almost half of the total privatization revenue came from the financial sector: 41 percent, in the banking sector, and nine percent, in the insurance sector.

What arises, then, is the crucial and urgent need to achieve greater efficiency and greater impact on government investments in social and economic programs. The systematic, continuous and effective evaluation of these programs can be a fundamental tool to achieve better results and provide a better use and control of the resources applied in them, in addition to providing social policy makers and program managers with important data for the program design of more consistent policies and for more effective public management.

Regardless of the crisis situation, performance evaluation has always been important in the public sector. To the extent that public services do not have a competitive consumer market that can serve as a measure of the quality and effectiveness of their provision, especially due to the behaviour of demand, the State is obliged to carry out a regular assessment of its programs and activities.

The State reform initiatives that have been carried out in all corners of the planet for more than a decade and a half bring with it a huge challenge: making it work better, but at a lower cost (Kettl, 1998: 74-6).

The search for this improvement involves assessing the performance of public programs, which gives rise to the possibility of evaluating the performance of the state apparatus. That is, when efficiency, effectiveness and effectiveness are established as measures of success of government action, it is also necessary to create means to evaluate different alternatives to obtain equivalent results (Kettl, 1998: 87)

Once the government starts to delegate to autonomous agencies and private companies the execution of its services, the need for evaluation grows. In fact, the privatization of public services and the growing autonomy granted to public agencies, requiring the adoption of forms of definition of performance in contracts, based on the previous definition of indicators and measures of success, imposes on the public administration the need to develop instruments and agile and low-cost evaluation methodologies, capable of offering managers more solid bases for decision-making in matters of public policies and society in general a more precise assessment of the performance of such agencies.

The evaluation of results therefore becomes a cornerstone in sustaining the reform of the State.

Evaluation of Public Programs

The definition of what is evaluation seems to be almost consensual. According to Unicef (1990), for example, this is the systematic and objective examination of a project or program, completed or in progress, which contemplates its performance, implementation and results, with a view to determining its efficiency, effectiveness, impact, sustainability and the relevance of its objectives. The purpose of the assessment is to guide decision makers, guiding them on the continuity, need for corrections or even suspension of a particular policy or program.

Criteria

If the evaluation is a way to measure the performance of programs, it is necessary to define measures to measure the obtained result. They are called evaluation criteria

and at this point the consensus on conceptual and methodological aspects in the field of program or public policy evaluation ends, giving rise to what could be called an authentic conceptual tangle, which represents an obstacle to more frequent use management tool in the public sector.

Although performance evaluation is normally associated with the measurement of efficiency in the management of public programs, this is clearly not the only and, eventually, nor the most important criterion to be used in the evaluation.

According to the Unicef manual, the most common are:

- Efficiency - a term originated in the economic science that means the lowest possible cost / benefit ratio for achieving the objectives set out in the program;
- Effectiveness - measure of the degree to which the program achieves its objectives and targets;
- Impact (or effectiveness) - indicates whether the project has (positive) effects on the external environment in which it intervened, in technical, economic, socio-cultural, institutional and environmental terms;
- Sustainability - measures the ability to continue the beneficial effects achieved through the social program, after its end;
- Cost / effectiveness analysis - similar to the idea of opportunity cost and the concept of pertinence; a comparison is made of alternative forms of social action to obtain certain impacts, in order to select that activity / project that meets the objectives with the lowest cost;
- Beneficiary satisfaction - assesses the user's attitude towards the quality of care he / she is getting from the program;
- Equity - seeks to assess the degree to which the benefits of a program are being distributed fairly and in line with the user's needs.

Indicators

The application of these criteria requires specific forms of operational actions, since they constitute indirect measures, that is, they must be calculated from the identification and quantification of the results obtained.

An attempt to systematize this discussion, while safeguarding the diversity inherent in the theme, can be found in Rob Vos (1993), who distinguishes, from a methodological point of view, at least three categories of social indicators: of result; input and access.

Result indicators reflect the levels of satisfaction of basic needs achieved. They are also called life-level indicators. For example: life expectancy, infant mortality, literacy, education and nutrition levels, among others.

Input indicators refer to the means (resources) available to obtain a certain standard of living. These means of meeting different basic needs may include, for example, in the field of nutrition, income and food availability; in the health field, the availability of drinking water, health centres and the number of doctors per inhabitant and; in the area of education, the number of schools and teachers per student.

Access indicators, on the other hand, identify the determinants that make it possible to make effective (and to what degree) the use of available resources to meet certain basic needs. For the purpose of evaluating social policies and programs, this third type of indicators is particularly relevant, since the existence of basic services does not guarantee universal access to them. In fact, it is common for factors that hinder the use of available services, such as, for example, geographic distance (especially in areas of dispersed population) and private costs related to the use of public services (school supplies, transport, medicines etc.). It is also possible to mention elements that are more difficult to quantify, such as the quality of services offered, cultural characteristics of the region, etc.

What to evaluate?

However, a crucial and preliminary question remains: what to evaluate?

According to Donald Kettl (1998: 87-92), the design of a public program or the action of a government agency can be synthesized in a sequence of definitions corresponding to successive degrees of aggregation of objectives, in the case mission> goals> objectives. Other authors will be able to hierarchize this sequence of aggregation of commitments in another way, placing the objectives after the mission (or purpose) and only then the goals.

This work adopts this last perspective, more consistent with the Brazilian tradition in that field (purpose> objective> goal> activity).

Taking as an example a public health program, the mission would consist of disease prevention, the objective could be defined as a vaccination campaign and the goal expressed as the commitment to vaccinate the entire population of pre-school age. Benchmarking can refer to the results of the programs, which would measure the scope of the mission or the products generated by the implementation of the programs.

The evaluation process will be facilitated and more useful if based on consistent planning, capable of establishing:

- causal relationships between activities and products; products and results that make it possible to achieve the intended goals;
- results that cause more or less precise effects and respond to the achievement of a specific objective; and effects that produce the impact intended by the purpose or mission of the program, in such a way as to seek to make the activities in fact contribute to the achievement of that same purpose.

It is the verification of these causal relationships that accounts for the consistency of planning and allows us to expect that intervention in a particular instance (or variable) of that process, as if a particular definition of activities, will produce a certain effect in a more comprehensive instance (or variable), as in the objective of a given program.

One way to allow the evaluation of public programs to contribute to test the planning consistency itself is through the previous definition of the program's logical matrix.² According to Wholey (1994: 15-20), the construction of the logical matrix begins with the identification of the general and specific objectives of the program and performance indicators (types of evidence) by which the program will be evaluated, as well as an indication of the data sources that will be used for measurements, comparisons and analysis:

In the North American literature, the terms program logic (program logic) or program structure (program design (Wholey et al., 1994) are common.

Secondly, the methodology of the logical matrix focuses on the identification of the resources (financial, human and infrastructure) allocated to the program, the activities planned, the expected results and the causal relationships (a particular combination of resources, allowing the carrying out a certain set of activities, which will lead to the production of certain results, which, presumably, will allow certain objectives associated with the program to be achieved) that the theory behind the program assumes can be assumed. Note that an important practical aspect in the development of the logical matrix is the identification of intermediate results (Wholey et al., 1994: 20) that associate certain activities of the program with one or more objectives of the same.

It is evident that evaluating performance through results (or long-term impacts) is more important (and politically tempting) when one wants to gauge the effective changes that a program could be promoting.

It happens, however, that it is almost always impossible to isolate the effect of factors external to the program on the changes that have occurred. In practice, evaluations of production (expressed in the logical matrix by the inputs and activities of the program) and of the immediate results are the only ones that effectively involve only the factors

(variables) that can be controlled by the program managers and that must be part of therefore, the management process.

The evaluation of results (or impacts) in the medium and long term, although it should not be disregarded, must be undertaken with more complex methodologies and implementation strategies, periodically complementing the production evaluation (Kettl, 1998).

Usual Evaluation Methodologies

Program evaluation experiences can be grouped, for analytical purposes, into three basic methodologies (Sulbrandt, 1993).

- Goal evaluation (production or product realization)

It is the most traditional type and its purpose is to measure the degree of success that a program.

- Impact assessment (scope of purpose or mission)

The impact assessment seeks to identify the effects produced on a target population of a social program. It seeks to verify not only whether the planned activities were carried out, but also whether the expected final results were also achieved. The focus of this type of study is, in summary, to detect changes in the living conditions of a target group or community, as a result of a program and the extent to which the changes occurred in the desired direction.

The central problem to be investigated in this case is the effectiveness of the program and, in order to achieve this goal, mechanisms are used to establish causal relationships between the actions of a program and the final result obtained. The purpose of this type of assessment can be defined as being to identify the net effects of a social intervention. As with the goal assessment, described earlier, this approach is carried out after the end of the program or stages of the program.

- Process evaluation

This type of evaluation systematically investigates the development of social programs in order to: measure the coverage of the social program; establish the degree to which the beneficiary population is reaching; and, mainly, to monitor its internal processes.

Its objective is to detect possible defects in the elaboration of procedures, to identify barriers and obstacles to their implementation and to generate important data for their reprogramming, through the registration of events and activities. Thus, the proper use of the information produced during the development of the program

allows changes to be made to its content during its execution. Contrary, therefore, to the previous approaches, this type of evaluation takes place simultaneously with the development of the program, and is also called formative evaluation.

Its application requires, however, that one can design the program flows and processes. In addition, it presupposes the existence of an adequate management information system, which served as a basis for the work of managers and evaluators at the appropriate time.

A complete evaluation system uses methodologies that provide for the evaluation of results and the evaluation of processes. In the sequence, the definitions and the operationalization forms used in the proposed model are presented.

Results assessment

Here, results are defined as consisting of immediate results, medium-term results (impacts) and long-term results (impacts). Thus, for the assessment, it is suggested the use of impact indicators to measure long-term results, related to the general objectives of the program and result indicators to measure immediate and medium-term results.

Result indicators measure the effects of the program: with the target population as a whole and with users of the program. In the first case, two types of result indicators should be surveyed, with field research or the aid of existing databases and / or records:

- Degree of general coverage

- measures the coverage rates of the target population by the program. Both the deficit and the surplus of beneficiaries are reasons for changes in the program's route.

The first demonstrates the need for expansion, and the second, that resources are being wasted (people ineligible as the target population are benefiting);

- Degree of differentiated coverage of the program - measures the differentiated participation of the subgroups of the proposed target population. This rate can portray the discrimination (or bias) in the selection of the program's customers based on region, age group, sex, etc.

As for the second point, that is, the evaluation of results with the users of the program, indicators for measuring benefits can be used, which take into account the specific objectives of each program or project. Rob Vos (1993) cites some examples of indicators most commonly used with program users and the target population:

- 1 - For nutrition programs - malnutrition rates by age group; mortality and morbidity;

2 - for education programs - illiteracy rates; repetition; evasion; schooling coefficients and levels of schooling;

3 - for health programs - mortality rates in general; infant mortality; maternal mortality; birth rate; fertility and life expectancy at birth;

4 - for housing programs - quantitative housing deficit; quality of housing construction and availability of basic services.

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5 - for nutrition programs - availability of food per person;

6 - for education programs - student / teacher relationships; student / school; number of grades offered by school and availability of teaching material per student;

7 - for health programs - number of doctors per inhabitant; of health posts per inhabitant; beds per inhabitant and vaccines available per inhabitant.

Access indicators, on the other hand, identify the determinants that make it possible to make effective use of the resources available in the programs to achieve the planned goals.

The most common are:

8 - for health programs - number of medical appointments per equivalent adult; geographical distance to the nearest health service; disposable income per family (useful data to enable the purchase of medicines, for example) and cultural factors;

9 - for education programs - distance from school; curricular adequacy and disposable income per family (to enable, for example, the purchase of school supplies).

In addition, the application of questionnaires allows measuring customer satisfaction, being a good indicator of quality, but not the only nor the most complete. In this sense, it is still possible to establish composite indicators through the construction of indices formed by a set of attributes defined based on the characteristics of the service.

Process evaluation

Process evaluation can be defined as the way to identify the true content of a public program, whether it is being carried out as intended, whether it is reaching the audience for which it was designed and whether the benefits are being distributed at the expected intensity (Scheirer , 1994: 40).

Therefore, process evaluation requires that methods be developed to answer three questions (Scheirer, 1994: 40-41): from what (and how) is the program in question? (methods for developing and specifying the components of a program); what is actually delivered to beneficiaries? (methods for measuring program implementation); why are there differences between the objectives (and intentions) of the program and those that are actually achieved? (evaluate factors that influence implementation, causing changes between expected and realized).

Components of a program

A complete and adequate description of the components of a program is essential to evaluate its execution. Components are the strategies, activities, behaviors, forms of communication and technologies necessary for the implementation of the program, as well as the specification of the beneficiaries and the situations in which the implementation takes place.

Program Identification

Adequate and accurate identification of program components will allow you to assess which aspects of the program were implemented as planned, which were not, and which factors influenced any discrepancies in implementation.

Another aspect that the correct specification of the components allows to assess concerns the extent to which the scope of the program (intended beneficiaries) was observed. In addition, it will make it possible to conjecture about the links between the results of the implementation and the results of the program itself (in terms of production, intermediate results, impacts, etc.).

An interesting aspect to be observed is that, while the specification (or detail) of the program content is a preliminary condition for the process evaluation, the very initiative of planning and carrying out the process evaluation contributes to a specification more realistic and appropriate content of the program.

Note that this is an important condition for, on the one hand, ensuring that the program is more effective (since the internal consistency of the program will have passed a preliminary sieve) and, on the other, that the evaluation of results and impact is more effective since the performance of the program will be compared with goals and more coherent and realistic expectations. To allow process evaluation to improve the design and specification of a public program, some techniques can be used.

1 - Formative evaluation: based on data collected from pilot projects and beneficiaries, during the course of a given intervention and which allows obtaining information on the feasibility of certain activities and instruments and the extent to which they are suitable for the planned design and the beneficiaries predicted;

2 - Verification of "evaluability": set of systematic processes for the adequate development of the theory underlying a given public program, and detail and clarify the expected uses for the data in the evaluation process, before the start of a full-scale evaluation. Its most important steps include (Scheirer, 1994: 49-50):

a) Involve key policy makers, managers and employees through a series of meetings to clarify their expectations for the program and for the evaluation itself;

b) Using a diagram model called a logical matrix, detail the expected causal relationships between three aspects of the program: allocated to the program, carrying out the specific activities foreseen the program and expected results;

c) Refinement of the theory underlying the program, by an interactive process, using visits to the project sites and available information, to examine the reality of field operations and the extent to which proposed theory is plausible;

d) Clarify the intended uses of the information obtained from the evaluation, through discussions with policy makers and program managers, including changes to the program itself.

e) Use of theory to assist in the specification of the program: application of theories relevant to the substantive theme that the program deals with, and the use of data to elucidate underlying processes. This type of process evaluation is important not only to specify the program content but also to link program activities with outcome measures (indicators) to be used in subsequent impact assessments.

The term theory here refers to interrelated principles that explain and make it possible to assume the behaviour of a person, group or organization. Chen (1990) distinguishes

two major types of theories: the normative, which defines what a program should be, and the causal, which empirically describes the causal relationships between proposed solutions (including contextual factors) and the results obtained.

Conclusion

The Government is proceeding with privatizations in order to obtain capital not only to pay foreign debts - in the case of Portugal to the IMF - but also presenting a public program of improvements for the population (health and education), for companies to boost the national economy, sacrificed the national strategic resources of a State, such as electricity production and distribution, ports, airports, airlines, banks, insurance companies, etc sold to foreign companies or citizens.

It is necessary to assess whether the programs that legitimized these sales were properly carried out, without corruption and with a criterion appropriate to their end.

Without the evaluation of public programs, the possibility of alienating strategic national assets opens up for the personal benefit of government members and public decision makers.

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